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A REVIEW OF SYSTEMATIC REVIEWS OF WORKPLACE
PROGRAMS FOR OBESITY PREVENTION

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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By

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ABSTRACT

Obesity in the United States is a major public health problem and adults are at a continued risk for weight gain. Obesity is prevalent in all employment groups, including health care personnel. Since many individuals spend a majority of their time at their place of employment, the worksite is an ideal place to promote and support healthy behaviors to improve health outcomes. This project presents the results of a review of nine systematic reviews that analyzed various interventions utilized in the workplace for obesity prevention or weight management purposes. A variety of interventions were supported by review findings; this include increasing physical activity, offering healthy food options in vending machines, and providing emotional support to those trying to change lifestyle behaviors, among many other options. These interventions achieved modest improvements when used alone. However, there is strong evidence to support the use of multicomponent interventions to assist with obesity prevention and weight management.

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BACKGROUND

Currently, more than one third (39.4%) of U.S. adults are obese (Ogden, Carroll, Kit, & Flegal, 2014). During the past 20 years, there has been a dramatic increase in obesity and the rates remain high. According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC; 2013), obesity percentages for the overall U.S. population were 23.1% in 1988-1994, 31.1% in 1999-2002, 34.1% in 2009-2012, and 35.7% in 2009-2012. Obesity can lead to chronic health conditions such as hypertension, heart disease, type II diabetes, sleep disorders, and stroke (Lavie, Milani, & Ventura, 2009), each of which contributes to the overall likelihood of mortality. As well as life-threatening chronic diseases, obesity contributes to high medical costs and premature death. In 2008, medical costs associated with obesity were estimated at \$147 billion; the medical costs for people who were obese were \$1,429 higher than those of normal weight (Finkelstein, Trogon, Cohen, & Dietz, 2009). Obesity was also responsible for the largest increase among causes of death between 1990 and 2000 (Mokdad, Marks, Stroup, & Gerberding, 2004).

Obesity in the United States is a major public health problem and adults are at a continued risk for weight gain over time (Lavie et al., 2009). Obesity is prevalent in all employment groups, including health care personnel. Obesity in the workplace accounts for more frequent absenteeism, sick leave, disability claims, and workplace injury and greater health care costs. Since employed health care workers spend approximately half of their lives at work, the worksite is a potential setting for programs that promote healthier behaviors such as weight loss. In his *Call to Action to Prevent and Decrease Overweight and Obesity*, the Surgeon General mentioned that the worksite is a setting in which the development and progress of healthy behaviors can be promoted (U.S.

Department of Health and Human Services, 2001). Promotion of healthy habits in the workplace has the potential for reducing absenteeism and lowering insurance rates

Worksite wellness programs have emerged in the United States primarily due to the relationships between health care coverage and the workplace (Thompson, Smith, & Bybee, 2005). Employers have increasingly offered worksite wellness programs to employees as a strategy to decrease costs of providing health care and improve employee productivity (Chan Osilla et al., 2012). Finkelstein et al. (2009) estimated that obesity was responsible for the almost \$40 billion increase in medical spending that had occurred up until 2006. In 2008, the estimated health care costs related to obesity were \$147 billion (Finkelstein et al., 2009). Healthy People 2010 and 2020 guidelines promote increasing the number of worksites that offer health promotion programs to their employees. The goals of these programs are to promote healthy lifestyles and prevent disease with educational and motivational approaches (Goetzel & Ozminkowski, 2008). The Healthy People 2010 goal was to increase the number of employers that offer a comprehensive health promotion program for employees to at least 75% (Linnan et al., 2008).

Problem Statement

The Nutrition and Weight Status objectives for Healthy People 2020 reflect strong science supporting the benefits of eating a healthful diet and maintaining a healthy body weight (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2010). The objectives also emphasize that efforts to change diet and weight should address individual behaviors as well as policies and environments that support these behaviors in settings such as schools, worksites, health care organizations, and communities (U.S. Department of Health and

Human Services, 2010). As new and innovative policies and environmental interventions to support healthy activities in the workplace are implemented, it is important to conduct a review of outcomes from workplace programs for obesity prevention and weight management strategies to determine which approaches are working and which are not.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this project was to synthesize outcomes from systematic reviews that have analyzed primary studies evaluating workplace programs for obesity prevention and weight management. This allowed an examination of approaches to addressing obesity that may be successful in worksites. The major aim of this project was to assess the effectiveness of obesity and weight management strategies that can be used in the workplace.

Supporting Framework

This project was guided by the worksite wellness model (Anderson et al., 2009). To improve health outcomes, many worksites support an assortment of activities that can be implemented to address obesity and weight management in the workplace. In addition, they have implemented organizational policies that reflect a commitment to support healthy behaviors in the workplace. No soda summers, increase water intake, or portion controls are some examples of worksite nutrition programs. These programs, along with physical activity, may occur alone or in conjunction with other programs that promote additional health objectives such as smoking cessation and stress management. Weight reduction may not be the main focus of some of the worksite health promotion programs.

The potential programmatic strategies stemming from worksite health promotion include environmental and health-related policy changes, informational messages, and

behavioral and social skills approaches (Anderson et al., 2009). Worksite environmental changes and policies are designed to make it easier to choose healthier options to aid in the prevention of obesity and weight management. By modifying the physical and/or organizational structure, worksite health promotion programs target the entire workforce instead of the individual. Environmental changes may include enhancing access to healthier foods, such as changing the content in vending machines, or enhancing physical activity by providing designated times for exercise. Policy changes within an organization may include time allotted for breaks and meals at the worksite or reimbursement for health club memberships. Informational and educational strategies attempt to supplement employee knowledge to make informed decisions about optimal weight management and obesity prevention. Health-related information provided on the company intranet, posters, and pamphlets about the benefits of a healthy diet and exercise are examples of information that may facilitate voluntary behavior changes that contribute to health, weight management, and obesity prevention. Behavioral and social skills approaches attempt to influence actions indirectly by targeting individual cognition believed to mediate behavior changes, such as awareness, self-efficacy, and perceived support (Anderson et al., 2009). The social environment found among worksites can provide support for people trying to initiate weight loss, maintain current healthy weight, or prevent obesity. Worksites can incorporate interventions such as group behavioral counseling, skill-building activities, and other uses of rewards and incentives to aid in the support for coworkers who are trying to prevent obesity or lose weight.

The worksite wellness model promotes activities that increase the well-being and self-actualization of individuals and groups. It represents a theoretical framework that

explores the factors and relationships that contribute to a health-promoting lifestyle.

(Figure 1 illustrates the key components of this model.) Understanding the factors that contribute to health-promoting behaviors is critical for developing the most appropriate interventions for obesity prevention, weight management, and maintaining a healthy lifestyle.

Figure 1. Worksite wellness model.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview

Worksite wellness is any workplace health promotion activity or organizational policy designed to support healthy behavior in the workplace and to improve health outcomes (CDC, 2013). According to the World Health Organization (1997), health promotion is the process of enabling people to increase control over and to improve their health. This activity can be implemented in the workplace as well as many other settings. Health promotion activities can include a variety of interventions such as health fairs, health education, medical screening, weight management programs, wellness newsletters, onsite fitness programs and/or facilities, and educational programs. Organizations that have worksite wellness programs typically have policies designed to facilitate employee health, including flex time for exercise, healthy food options in vending machines, and financial and other incentives for participation. Worksite wellness has been expanded over the past decade to encompass the overall creation of a “culture of health” within the worksite (DeVries, 2010, p. 48). The importance of the worksite as a setting for health promotion is supported by the World Health Organization (2008).

Physical Activity

The most common workforce health promotion program strategies pertain to physical activity, fitness, and exercise programs. Fitness programs have been reported to reduce the risk of disease, enhance personal function, and promote mental health and have proven to be most beneficial in terms of employee and employer satisfaction (Voit, 2001). Positive outcomes have been reported in other studies with regard to physical activity. These outcomes included reduced waist circumference, decreased body fat and

body mass index (BMI), reduction in blood pressure and cholesterol, and increased fruit and vegetable consumption (Aldana et al., 2005; Atlantis, Chow, Kirby, & Singh, 2006; Chyou, Scheuer, & Linneman, 2006, Hammond, Leonard, & Fridinger, 2000; Pohjonen & Ranta, 2001; Proper, Hildebrandt, VanderBeek, Twisk, & Mechelen, 2003).

There have been several studies discussing the effects of health interventions at worksites. The studies examined whether a specific intervention had an effect on a health objective, such as obesity. Pedometer-based programs are prevalent in many areas of worksite wellness programs (Tudor-Locke & Bassett, 2004). The pedometer involves wearing a device to record the number of steps taken daily. The pedometer has a competitive nature with a goal setting component, such as completion of 10,000 steps per day, and the employer has a website for logging steps.

A meta-analysis of pedometer-based program evaluations across all worksite settings indicated that, on average, such programs increased step counts by 27%, decreased BMI by $0.38\text{kg}/\text{m}^2$, and lowered systolic blood pressure by 3.8 mmHG (Bravata et al., 2007). Five separate studies of pedometer-based workplace programs conducted by different research teams (Chan, Ryan, & Tudor-Locke, 2004; Freak-Poli, Wolfe, Backholer, de Courten, & Peeters, 2011; Kwak et al., 2010; Morgan et al., 2011; Touger-Decker, Denmark, Bruno, O'Sullivan-Maillet, & Lasser, 2010) found improvements in participant waist circumference. Another evaluation of a 4-month pedometer-based physical activity program revealed improvements in risk factors for diabetes and cardiovascular disease (Freak-Poli et al., 2011). In addition, there were also improvements in meeting physical activity guidelines, waist circumference, blood pressure, and vegetable consumption. The study sample had a 1.6 cm reduction in waist

circumference. These health outcomes were observed among males as well as females in all age ranges. Based on multiple research studies, pedometer-based programs can help to promote low-impact physical activity in the workplace. Pedometer-based programs have demonstrated improvements in lowering risk factors for diabetes and cardiovascular disease by improving physical activity levels, reducing systolic blood pressure, and improving waist circumference.

Roberts (2009) described the impact of a preseason work task-specific fitness program among reforestation workers in western Canada. This fitness program, called the Fit to Plant program, included aerobic and resistance training 8 weeks prior to planting season. After 5 years of implementing the program by the Weyerhaeuser Company, the results indicated a significant increase in cardiorespiratory fitness and productivity and a reduction from 22% to less than 5% in injury and illness rate among tree planters.

Nutrition

Nutrition plays an important role in weight loss, weight management, and obesity prevention. Beresford et al. (2001) evaluated worksite change in fruit and vegetable consumption using a theoretically based behavioral intervention among 28 worksites in Seattle. The Seattle 5 a Day worksite intervention encouraged people to eat more fruits and vegetables along a timeline suggested by the stages of change model. Fruit and vegetable intake of employees at the worksite was assessed and compared at baseline and at a 2-year follow-up. The study findings indicated that there was a difference of 0.2 for the control worksites, with an intervention effect of 0.3 daily servings ($p < .05$). There was a significant increase in fruit and vegetable consumption in the intervention worksites. In this randomized control design study, body weight was not assessed as a

study outcome. In a 1-year study, French et al. (2010) achieved significant increases in the purchasing of health snacks by lowering their prices 50% and by enhancing their promotion as healthy food to eat between meals. Both the Beresford et al. and French et al. studies did not monitor body weight. Thus, effects from these workplace interventions on weight outcomes are unknown.

Cost Effectiveness

There is a relationship between excess weight and high medical expenditures (Finkelstein et al., 2009). There are long-term cost benefits of worksite wellness programs. The Community Guide Task Force released the results of a comprehensive and systematic literature review that analyzed the economic impacts of worksite wellness programs on health, weight management, and obesity prevention (Goetzel & Ozminkowski, 2008). In a review of worksite wellness programs from the 1980s and 1990s, there was an estimated return on investment savings from \$1.40 to \$3.14 per dollar spent on the program (Goetzel, Juday, & Ozminkowski, 1999). In an analysis of the financial impact of health promotion programs, Aldana (2001) reviewed 32 studies and found that only four studies reported no positive effects on health care costs related to worksite wellness programs and health promotion efforts. A randomized design was not utilized in those four studies. The remaining 28 studies that reported positive results applied experimental or rigorous quasi-experimental methods as part of the investigations. Aldana also evaluated the impact of worksite wellness programs on absenteeism and found reductions in employee absenteeism no matter the research design used. He also reported the range of return on investment from \$2.50 to \$10.10 saved for every dollar invested.

Chapman (2005) summarized results from 56 financial impact studies conducted over the past 2 decades and found that employees who participated in worksite wellness programs had 25%-30% lower medical and absenteeism costs compared with nonparticipants (Chapman, 2005). These findings were over an average period of 3.6 years. These higher estimates of cost savings may be inflated due to Chapman including a mix of cross-sectional and prospective research studies in his analysis. In contrast to Aldana's (2001) study, Chapman's review did not account for study design.

Summary

The review of literature indicated that worksite health promotion programs that targeted employees in a worksite setting showed promising results in affecting positive behavioral change. Studies demonstrated improvements in exercise and dietary behaviors resulting from worksite health promotion programs. Fruit and vegetable servings per day increased significantly. According to 2009 data from the Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance System, an estimated 32.5% of Americans consumed two or more servings of fruits per day and 26.3% consumed three or more vegetables per day (CDC, 2010). The long-term cost benefits of worksite wellness programs have been well-documented in the literature. Research findings have demonstrated a reduction in medical care expenditures and lower absenteeism. Worksite wellness programs have resulted in a positive return on investment per dollar invested within a few years of program implementation.

METHODS

In this doctoral project, a critical analysis of systematic reviews was conducted to examine health promotion interventions and approaches to addressing obesity in the worksite. According to the hierarchy of evidence guidelines by the Centre for Evidence-Based Medicine at Oxford University (Oxford Centre for Evidence-Based Medicine Levels of Evidence Working Group, 2011), a systematic review of randomized controlled trials is the strongest source of evidence based on the relative strength of the studies considered in a review of research. Thus, systematic reviews are valuable and useful sources of information about the effectiveness of interventions associated with obesity prevention and weight management. These reviews can provide strong evidenced-based information and data about the effectiveness of worksite wellness programs when considering implementation of certain interventions in the worksite.

Search Strategies

Several key words were used to search for systematic reviews on worksite wellness programs and obesity prevention including *obesity*, *worksite wellness*, and *workplace wellness*. Combinations of search terms including *worksite wellness programs*, *obesity prevention*, *workplace and weight management*, and *workplace and obesity prevention* were used to search three computerized databases: Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL), PubMed, and Science Direct. The search was accomplished with the assistance of a California State University librarian.

The inclusion criteria for articles selected for this project included systematic review articles that focused on weight management and obesity prevention and were published between the years 2004 and 2014. Searches were limited to literature published

in English which focused on adults. This search identified 26 systematic reviews. Nineteen reviews were excluded for the following reasons. Three reviews were excluded due to their focus on adults with intellectual disabilities. Two systematic reviews covered pediatric obesity although the search criteria specified adults. Six reviews were omitted because their focus was on the elderly and pharmacological agents involving weight gain. One review only analyzed fruit intake and body weight. Another review only investigated bariatric surgery as a strategy. Two reviews centered on one-on-one care and were specifically geared toward medical doctors. One study had an emphasis on epidemiology and another one discussed pregnancy-related obesity. Although one study was published in the United States, it was excluded because of its focus on the management of obesity in Scotland. There were seven systematic reviews remaining. Four additional reviews were identified through reference mining of those articles and identifying the terms worksite or workplace in the title of the reference. Of the 26 systematic reviews found during the initial search, a total of 11 systematic reviews were reviewed (see Figure 2).

Extraction of Data From Systematic Reviews

The 11 selected manuscripts abstracted as systematic reviews were read and each was critically appraised to determine its validity and potential usefulness. Some of the 11 manuscripts included both research studies as well as meta-analysis studies. The evidence from the selected systematic reviews was considered in context using the Polit and Beck (2012) hierarchy of evidence. The strongest form of evidence, according to Polit and Beck, is categorized as Level I or II. These are systematic reviews of randomized control trials and meta-analyses. A moderate level of validity and reliability associated with the research evidence presented in a study is found in Levels III and IV. These two levels

Figure 2. Flowchart of search and screening process. Adapted from “Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses: The PRISMA Statement,” by D. Moher, A. Liberati, J. Tetzlaff, D. G. Altman, & the PRISMA Group, 2009, *PLoS Medicine*, 6(7), p. e1000097. Copyright 2009 by Moher et al.

include studies from well-designed trials without randomization and nonexperimental studies involving more than one center or research group. Levels VI and VII are considered the weakest types of research. These studies include opinions from respected authorities based on clinical evidence, descriptive studies or reports from communities, and views from colleagues and peers. Therefore, the ideal source of evidence is a Level I study in the form of a systematic review. The major advantage of systematic reviews is that they are based on the findings of multiple studies that were identified in comprehensive, systematic literature searches.

Critical Appraisal Assessment Strategy

In order to appraise worth of systematic reviews, the investigator reviewed various appraisal tools to evaluate systematic research studies. To appraise the methodological quality of the included reviews, the decision was made to use the strategies suggested by the Joanna Briggs Institute for evidence-based nursing and midwifery in an article titled *Changing Practice: Evidence Based Practice Information Sheets for Health Professionals: Appraising Systematic Reviews* (Joanna Briggs Institute, 2000). Questions posed in Table 1 provided the framework for the critical appraisal of the research studies selected in this project. The evaluation questions covered eight essential components that were used to review and score the systematic reviews. These components included the following: review question, search strategy, inclusion criteria, critical appraisal, data synthesis, similarity of studies, report of findings, and conclusions and recommendations. The investigator developed a rating for each of the 21 questions using a yes or no response with a corresponding score of 1 or 0.

Table 1

Scoring for Appraisal of Included Reviews

Concept	Questions	Scoring
Review Question	Is the review question clearly stated?	Score 0 = No 1 = Yes
Search Strategy	Were comprehensive search methods used to locate studies? Was a thorough search done of appropriate databases, and were other potentially important sources explored?	Score 0 = No 1 = For each yes
Inclusion Criteria	How were studies selected?	Score 0 = Not identified 1 = Clearly explained
Critical Appraisal	Was the validity of studies assessed appropriately?	Score 0 = No 1 = Yes
Data Synthesis	How were the studies combined? Were the findings combined appropriately?	Score 0 = No 1 = Yes
Similarity of Studies	Were the populations of the different studies similar? Was the same intervention evaluated by the individual studies? Were the same outcomes used to determine the effectiveness of the intervention being evaluated? Were reasons for differences between studies explored?	Score 0 = No 1 = For each yes
Report of Findings	Are review methods clearly documented? Is the review question clearly and explicitly stated? Was the search strategy reported? Were the inclusion criteria reported? Were the criteria for appraising studies reported? Were the methods used to combine studies reported?	Score 0 = No 1 = For each yes
Conclusions and Recommendations	Is a summary of findings provided? Are specific directives for new research proposed? Were the recommendations supported by the reported data?	Score 0 = No 1 = For each yes
Total points possible		21

Note. Adapted from the Joanna Briggs Institute for evidence-based nursing and midwifery.

RESULTS

The 11 identified systematic reviews were individually read, thoroughly reviewed, analyzed, and organized as a part of the data analysis phase. Each review article was read and given a score based on the eight essential components noted in Table 1. A total score was obtained by adding the points awarded for each question. As a measure of quality control and to minimize the risk of bias, each individual review was scored by this investigator as well as an independent reviewer using the Joanna Briggs Institute appraisal strategy. This second reviewer was an experienced researcher and nursing educator. Each article could achieve a maximum of 21 points. Prior to starting the article reviews, the decision was made to rate the worth or quality of the systematic review article based on the scores assigned by the two reviewers using the following rubric: scores of 0-12 indicated a study judged to be of low quality, scores of 13-17 indicated a study believed to exhibit moderate quality, and scores of 18-21 were judged to represent a high quality systematic review article. If the scores of the project's author and the external reviewer differed in their independent evaluation of an article by 1 or 2 points, an average score was calculated. The two reviewers' scores were compared and discussed until a consensus was obtained.

The lowest score of the 11 articles was a 17. One study had scores that varied between the investigator and the expert reviewer by 3 points. Five studies received the same score and the remaining five studies varied by 1 point. After careful review by the author and the expert reviewer, two studies were eliminated because they did not address interventions utilized in a workplace setting. A final total of 9 articles were reviewed.

Table 2 shows the methodological quality scores based on the review criteria shown in Figure 2.

Specific information was collected from each of the nine studies selected for this review of systematic research studies on the topic of worksite obesity prevention and/or intervention programs. Key points, methodological considerations, and variables identified in the systematic review studies included the following:

- Publication details (e.g., year of publication)
- Characteristics of study (e.g., study design, methods, setting, sample size, inclusion and exclusion criteria)
- Characteristics of the population (e.g., age, gender, ethnicity, total number of participants)
- Details about the exposure/intervention (e.g., type and category; change targets in terms of cognitive, emotional, or physiological changes targeted and/or assessed in process evaluations; mode of delivery)
- Outcome measures (e.g., methods of assessing outcomes, duration, main findings—especially effectiveness, summaries, and analyses related to the content and effectiveness of the interventions studied)

This information was extracted from each of the nine reviews, summarized, and included in the Table of Evidence (TOE; Table 3). The primary objective of this review of systematic reviews was to provide an overview of various interventions and strategies utilized in worksites to assist with obesity prevention, weight management, and healthy lifestyles. Components of the interventions could have included diet and nutrition, exercise and physical activity, and behavioral skills and social support. This reviewer

Table 2

Systematic Review Critical Appraisal Scores of Project Articles

Author/Year	Author Critical Appraisal Score	Reviewer Critical Appraisal Score	Agreement by Reviewers for TOE Inclusion
Anderson et al. (2009)	19	20	Yes
Osei-Assibey, Kyrou, Adi, Kumar, & Matyka (2010)	21	20	Yes
Freak-Poli et al. (2011)	19	20	Yes
Griffiths, Anigbogu, & Nanchahal (2012)	20	21	Deleted as not worksite program
Gudzune, Hutfless, Maruthur, Wilson, & Segal (2013)	21	21	Yes
Kirk, Penney, McHugh, & Sharma (2012)	21	18	Yes, with reservations; limitations noted in TOE
Kremers et al. (2010)	19	19	Yes
Lemmens, Oenema, Klepp, Henriksen, & Brug (2008)	17	18	Deleted as not worksite program
Loveman et al. (2011)	20	21	Yes, with limitations noted in TOE
Mehta et al. (2013)	19	19	Yes
Soler et al. (2010)	21	21	Yes

Table 3

TOE: Systematic Reviews of Worksite Weight Loss Programs

Author/ Year	Interventions	Key Findings/Meta-Analytic Results	Conclusions	Comments
Anderson et al. (2009)	Behavioral skills and social support Educational—informational messages Environmental and policy changes	15 studies reported a change in weight of 3 pounds at 6-12 months, a change in BMI (0.4), and change in body fat of a 1% decrease at 12 months	Evidence of a modest reduction in weight loss from worksite programs that include nutrition, physical activity, or both	Information along with behavioral counseling offers more benefit than providing information alone
Osei-Assibey et al. (2010)	Educational—printed material on diet and weight loss Behavioral skills and social support—personalized messages and material Physical activity—moderate to vigorous 3-4 x per week	Weight loss in the tailored intervention group was significant from baseline ($p = .03$) Weight change at 6 months in the intervention versus the control group (-1.3 vs. 1.1 kg; $p < .05$), with a mean difference of -2.4 kg ($p < .01$)	Evidence shows positive weight management results related to a variety of dietary and lifestyle approaches	Culturally tailored lifestyle interventions can produce significant weight loss as compared to standard care. Small sample sizes and lack of follow-up data
Freak-Poli et al. (2011)	Physical activity—pedometer usage for increasing physical activity in the workplace	The mean BMI in the intervention group was 0.92 lower (1.82 to 0.02 lower) than the control group	Limited and low quality evidence to support the effectiveness of pedometers in increasing physical activity	Unable to draw positive conclusions about pedometer based on interventions in the workplace

Table 3. (continued)

Author/ Year	Interventions	Key Findings/Meta- Analytic Results	Conclusions	Comments
Gudzune et al. (2013)	Environmental and policy changes— decreased prices of health foods available at worksite and motivational materials to promote stair use Physical activity— formation of walking groups	5 studies evaluated change in BMI from baseline to 12 and 24 months. BMI change of 0.2 kg/m ² Combination interventions prevented weight gain of ≥ 0.5 kg over 12 months	Low to moderate evidence to support prevention of weight gain in work- and college-based interventions	Agree with authors' findings. There was risk of bias from nonrandomized interventions and lack of blinding of outcome assessors
Kirk et al. (2012)	Behavioral skills and social support—dietary counseling and motivation and encouragement by health professionals Educational— computer-tailored nutrition education Physical activity— moderate intensity physical activity	Behavioral treatment of obesity produced an initial weight loss of 5%-10% Low-carbohydrate diets were more effective in inducing weight loss after 6 months, although the effect was not sustained at 12 months More than 250 minutes per week of physical activity could promote clinically significant weight loss	Programs should target weight management instead of physical outcomes Calorie- controlled diets promote greater weight loss than low-fat diets. 150-250 minutes per week of moderate physical activity to prevent weight gain	Multicomponent interventions are more successful at preventing weight gain

Table 3. (continued)

Author/ Year	Interventions	Key Findings/Meta- Analytic Results	Conclusions	Comments
Kremers et al. (2010)	Behavioral skills and social support—motivation and encouragement to diet and exercise and motivation to increase empowerment	Program goal aimed at weight management is more successful than goal of preventing CVD or improving general health ($p = .01$)	Interventional studies are not designed to show long-term effects on weight-related outcomes	Agree with authors' findings that programs need to be evaluated for a period of 5 years or longer in order to assess the sustainability of behavior change on the effects on weight that resulted from the program The authors did not specify what types of studies were analyzed
Loveman et al. (2011)	Multicomponent weight management programs—diet, physical activity, and behavior change strategies	5 RCTs compared multicomponent interventions with nonactive comparison groups Weight change was greater in the intervention group. High physical activity intervention resulted in a greater weight loss than the diet alone intervention	Weight loss was small and not indicative of clinically significant reduction in weight	Conclusions as to the outcomes of the interventions are difficult to make based on the differences between the studies, their interventions, and the lengths of follow-up
Mehta et al. (2013)	Education—45-minute nutrition program involving nutrition counseling Physical activity—brief period of group exercise in the workday (10-minute exercise break)	Three interventions had significant outcomes in BMI, three in weight, two in waist circumference, and one in waist-to-hip ratio	Most successful interventions encouraged lifestyle changes by providing a time and a place to perform physical activity or giving educational classes with individual dietary advice	The studies were pre-post design and lacked a control group The interventions involved employees in a higher socioeconomic group; therefore, they have limited generalizability

Table 3. (continued)

Author/ Year	Interventions	Key Findings/Meta- Analytic Results	Conclusions	Comments
Soler et al. (2010)	Behavioral skills and social support—collection of information about health behaviors or indicators via questionnaires or from medical records. Health behaviors included alcohol use, diet and nutrition, physical activity, seat belt use, and tobacco use	11 studies included dietary behaviors and reported an 11.2 percentage point change ($p < .001$) for subjects who decreased their fat intake when compared to an untreated comparison group 14 studies that included physical activity outcomes showed favorable intervention effects	Effect size estimates from all studies including dietary behaviors was small Only three studies analyzing physical activity included comparison groups Most studies showed little to no change in body weight or BMI	Agree with the authors that most effect estimates were too small and results were based on before-and-after studies with no comparison groups Questionable whether AHRF had meaningful health effects
	Educational—the personal assessment of health habits and risk factors and feedback—verbally or in writing	17 studies measured body composition as an outcome and reported an increase in BMI and/or weight gain		
	Physical activity			

Note. AHRF = assessment of health risks with feedback, BMI = body mass index, CVD = cardiovascular disease, and RCT = random clinical trial.

sought to summarize the evidence based on the effectiveness of workplace interventions on health and healthy behaviors in relation to weight management, obesity prevention, and/or weight loss. She was also interested in any other covariates that might be associated with the outcomes of interest.

The results of this review provided an overview of the various interventions and strategies utilized in worksites to assist with obesity prevention, weight management, and healthy lifestyles. A detailed inspection of each of the nine studies was undertaken to identify and classify the interventions used in workplace settings. The TOE (Table 3) gives additional details about each included article. The various interventional components identified in the systematic reviews included behavioral skills and social support, diet and nutrition, education on exercise and other forms of physical activity, and environmental and policy changes. Many of the studies analyzed multicomponent interventions for weight loss and/or weight management.

DISCUSSION, IMPLICATIONS FOR PRACTICE, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Discussion

Four of the nine reviews analyzed behavioral skills and/or social support. Anderson et al. (2009) reviewed studies utilizing structured programs for behavioral skills development and/or physical activity. They analyzed structured programs such as scheduled individual sessions or group sessions versus unstructured self-directed approaches. Their findings indicated that offering structured programs appeared to more effective than unstructured approaches and providing additional behavioral counseling had a greater benefit than providing information alone. There was no significant difference in the program effectiveness based on whether the counseling intervention was initiated by a lay person versus a professional group leader.

The Kirk, Penney, McHugh, and Sharma (2012) review demonstrated that offering structured, individual nutritional counseling to reduce fat or caloric intake was instrumental in weight loss as compared with usual care. The dietary counseling interventions produced modest weight losses within the first 12-month period; however, the impact did not continue over time during the follow-up period. One of the reviews included motivational interventions within the study; however, this variable was not assessed as to its effect on the outcome measures of interest. In the Soler et al. (2010) review, the authors evaluated the effects of an Assessment of Health Risks with Feedback when used either alone or with other additional intervention components. The studies examined by Soler et al. used a before-and-after study design, which is believed to be the least suitable research design, which made it difficult to draw conclusions regarding the effectiveness of using assessments of health risks with feedback in worksite settings.

Health education about diet and nutrition was analyzed in four of the nine reviews. Tailored interventions versus standard/usual care were analyzed in the Osei-Assibey, Kyrou, Adi, Kumar, and Matyka (2010) review. The tailored intervention group received monthly outpatient visits along with the use of personalized messages and materials, information on weight loss, and six biweekly classes on healthy eating, increasing physical activity, and low-fat high-fiber diets. The usual care group received nothing more than regular medical care with no special or specific instructions. Weight loss in the tailored intervention group was significantly different from the control group. For data synthesis, a quality of reporting of meta-analysis was conducted; however, the results could not be pooled.

The Internet has become a means of access for information on health and nutrition. Computer-tailored health and nutrition education has shown strong promise as an interventional strategy, particularly in achieving short-term outcomes (Kirk et al., 2012). The actual degree of effectiveness of web-based interventions has not been determined through exact research science, but the Internet is believed to be an effective resource to deliver health information based on personal stories and expert opinion. A nutrition program intervention involving nutrition counseling for obese hospital employees was analyzed in the Mehta et al. (2013) review. Employees attended five 45 - minute nutrition education sessions conducted by a doctor, nurse, dietician, and/or exercise physiologist. The interventions employed in the Mehta et al. (2013) review utilized a pre-post design methodology and lacked a control group, which posed a threat to internal validity.

Of the nine reviews, five analyzed worksite programs involving physical activity interventions. Results of most of the reviews suggested that physical activity interventions had a significant and positive effect on weight loss and weight management. In one study, the intervention group received a culturally tailored weight loss activity program which included exercising at a moderate to vigorous level for a minimum of three to four times per week and for at least 30 minutes each session. Another study utilized a brief period of group exercise in the workday that included a 10-minute exercise break. In one study, the control group was given weekly newsletters on general health topics. Some studies did not have a control or comparison group. Osei-Assibey et al. (2010) found a weight change at 6 months in the intervention group versus the control group (-1.3 vs. 1.1 kg; $p < .05$), with a mean difference of -2.4 kg ($p < .01$). Most studies that included physical activity outcomes showed favorable intervention effects similar to the above results.

Freak-Poli et al. (2011) analyzed the effects of using pedometers to increase physical activity in workplace settings. Four studies in the Freak-Poli et al. review assessed weight-related outcomes for 3 to 6 months after the pedometer intervention. The results for physical activity could not be combined during a meta-analysis approach because each of the four studies used a different measure of activity. Because of this lack of a consistent outcome measure, there was insufficient evidence to assess the effectiveness of using a pedometer in the workplace to increase physical activity.

Some of the studies analyzed multicomponent interventions for weight loss or weight management. The multicomponent interventions included dietary counseling, physical activity promotion, and/or behavioral change. In the Kirk et al. (2012) study,

they reviewed randomized controlled trials to determine the long-term effectiveness of physical activity and exercise with and without diet and/or behavior modification therapy. The results of the multicomponent interventions led to a greater weight loss, whereas single-component interventions were more effective in improving the targeted behavior. Three-component interventions were shown to have more success associated with obesity prevention than one- or two-component interventions.

In summary, the purpose of this author's review was to synthesize outcomes from systematic reviews that had analyzed studies evaluating workplace programs for obesity prevention and weight management and to determine the most effective and promising interventions used in this type of setting. The aim of this project was to assess the effectiveness of obesity and weight management strategies that could be used in the workplace. The available interventions analyzed were behavioral skills and social support, educational messages or classes, environmental and policy changes, and physical activity and exercise. The findings from this review showed that the interventions available and used in worksite settings varied and not all contributed to a successful reduction in weight or obesity prevention.

This author found most worksites that offered nutrition and physical activity programs achieved modest improvements in weight status during the intervention period of 6 months. That finding is encouraging as any improvement in weight management is better than no improvement. However significant results were not seen on follow-up or there was a lack of follow-up data. Behavioral counseling along with nutritional information was shown to offer more benefit than providing information alone. The research suggested that individuals need to be engaged in programs that last longer than 5

years to assess the sustainability of behavior change on weight loss and/or maintenance of a healthy weight. Therefore, it is essential to provide follow-up on worksite programs for at least 5 years or longer. In a few of the studies, it was difficult to draw conclusions. Also, a meta-analysis of the interventions could not be performed because of small sample sizes, differences between the studies, the variety of interventions used, and the varying lengths of follow-up. In addition, some of the studies had a pre-post design with a lack of a control group. Overall, this review of systematic reviews demonstrated that worksite programs resulted in a modest improvement in health status based on any number of strategies utilized in worksite promotion programs. Any improvement, though modest, is welcomed considering the magnitude of the obesity epidemic facing Americans.

Implications for Practice

The goal of this author was to look for interventions that could be utilized in a worksite wellness program within the public health department to help prevent obesity and/or maintain a healthy body weight. The interventions analyzed in this review would be used to improve health-related behaviors and health outcomes among the employees of the public health department. This review suggested that worksite interventions should include environmental and policy changes, informational and educational messages, and behavioral skills and social support. Environmental changes would include enhancing access to healthier foods, such as changing the content in vending machines. Vending machines could no longer offer sodas and/or other sugary drinks for consumption. Other changes could include providing more nutritional snacks in vending machine besides chips and/or cookies. A policy change could include enhancing physical activity by

providing designated times for exercise. One study in this review provided a designated timeframe for a 10-minute exercise break while on duty. This break could be incorporated into the daily schedule and also added to the weekly and/or monthly staff meetings. When it comes to physical activity, one of the practice recommendations is that individuals should engage in 150-250 minutes per week of moderate intensity physical activity to prevent weight gain and maintain long-term weight. A physical activity break incorporated within the worksite wellness program could help promote physical activity.

Informational messages and educational strategies help supplement employee knowledge to make informed decisions about optimal weight management and obesity prevention. Health-related information provided on the company intranet, posters in the hallways and in the employee break room, and pamphlets about the benefits of a healthy diet and exercise are examples of information that may facilitate voluntary behavior changes that contribute to health, weight management, and obesity prevention.

Behavioral and social skills approaches attempt to influence actions indirectly by targeting individual cognition believed to mediate behavior changes, such as awareness, self-efficacy, and perceived support (Anderson et al., 2009). The public health department has employed physicians, nurses, community workers, clerks, and other ancillary personnel who are knowledgeable about nutrition and exercise. This review suggests that worksite programs should incorporate individual sessions that focus on behavior modification and lifestyle changes, such as modifying physical activity, diet, and thinking habits that contribute to obesity among employees. Behavioral and social support interventions have been effective in inducing an initial weight loss of around 5%-10%.

In summary, employers with worksite wellness programs have the methods and means to promote healthy behaviors, improve employees' health, and promote obesity prevention and weight management amongst its employees. The worksite is the ideal location in which physical activity and other health-related behaviors can be promoted and consistently reach an immense number of employees over an extended period of time, thus promoting the probability of successful outcomes. Health department employees can serve as role models for the community in which they serve. The emphasis on the overall health of the individual is the key to the prevention of obesity. A public health department that models healthy lifestyles is important.

Recommendations

This author's recommendations are that worksite wellness programs should be set up using a worksite wellness model similar to Figure 1. The components should include worksite interventions such as environmental and policy changes, informational messages, and behavioral skills and social support. Healthy People 2020 is the second 10-year national initiative focusing on obesity to improve the health of all Americans. The objectives found in Healthy People 2010 can be used to focus employers' efforts and measure worksite outcomes against national benchmarks. As defined by Healthy People, comprehensive workplace health programs should contain the following five elements:

1. Health education, which focuses on skill development and lifestyle behavior change along with information dissemination and awareness building, preferably tailored to employees' interests and needs.

2. Supportive social and physical environments that include an organization's expectations regarding healthy behaviors and policies that promote health and reduce risk of disease.
3. Integrating the worksite program into your organization's structure.
4. Linkage to related programs like employee assistance programs (EAPs) and programs to help employees balance work and family.
5. Worksite screening programs ideally linked to medical care to ensure follow-up and appropriate treatment as necessary. (CDC, n.d., p. 2)

In conclusion, the strategies of a worksite wellness program should be implemented in the context of a supportive environment, which favors regard for concurrent implementation of individual, organizational, and environmental strategies. Those developing a worksite obesity prevention program should assess for facilitators and barriers to the proposed interventions and seek employee participation. Incentive strategies (e.g., gift cards, free gym memberships, team challenges, and reduced insurance premiums) have been shown to increase employee participation and attainment of desired outcomes, such as weight loss, weight maintenance, and increased physical activity. Sound, effective interventions for obesity prevention and weight management will continue to emerge, develop, and transform as new evidence-based interventions emerge through continued research. Therefore, health care providers should be alert to new interventions for promoting health lifestyle behaviors that will continue to motivate individuals in the worksite.

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